

D7.4 Data Management Plan (update 1)

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Control Sheet

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Peer review

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About AWARE2ALL

We face the challenge of future highly automated vehicles, where occupants can move freely to engage in non-driving activities. This new environment prompts questions about how car occupants will actually sit, what activities they will engage in, and how they will be informed through the HMI to keep them in the loop if necessary.

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards the deployment of Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) in traffic, by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and changes in the interaction of different road users caused by the emergence of HAV through the development of innovative technologies along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies.

AWARE2ALL will develop safety and HMI systems that will be interrelated to achieve a holistic understanding of the scene and to ensure safe operation of the HAV. AWARE2ALL proposes a common conceptual universal safety framework for considering Human Machine Interaction (HMI). The project will be built on the results of projects funded under H2020 and other R&D programmes addressing the identification of new safety-critical situations and the most likely positions and postures considering the expected HAV applications.

The main objective of AWARE2ALL is to address the new safety challenges posed by the introduction of HAVs in mixed road traffic, through the development of inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

AWARE2ALL includes 16 partners from 6 EU Member States (ES, DE, GR, NL, FR and SE) and 2 associated countries (TR, CS) and it is complemented by the International Advisory Board (IAB) representing key stakeholders that covers the full research and industrial development automotive value chain, more specifically in the CCAM field.

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Executive Summary

WP7 of AWARE2ALL project will ensure an efficient overall management of the project. In particular, Task 7.4 is devoted to data management procedures. This deliverable, D7.4 - Data Management Plan (update 1) aims at providing an update of D7.2 and presents the information that has been updated since its submission, mainly Section 3.

The objective of the DMP is to provide guidelines that will define simple and practical pointers during the implementation and validation stages of the project, support compliance with underlying legal obligations and promote the adoption of best data management practices.

The deliverable has been structured according to the EC's guidelines as follows:

- Chapter 1 – Introduction to AWARE2ALL project's concept and approach, and to the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 – Data Management describes the purpose of the DMP, its relation to the project objectives, and the DMP online tool.
- Chapter 3 – Description of the types of data to be generated by the project and classified by demonstration.
- Chapter 4 – FAIR data explains how data will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and re-used.
- Chapter 5 – Allocation of resources explains how allocation of required resources for data management is implemented.
- Chapter 6 – Data protection and ethical aspects details the methodology to be followed to reach compliancy with data protection regulation and consideration of ethical aspects.
- Chapter 7 – Data Security explains the approach towards guaranteeing data security.
- Chapter 8 – Conclusion.

Acronyms and terms

Acronym	Definition
AEB	Autonomous Emergency Braking
ASAM	Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DL	Deep Learning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMPO	Data Manager and Protection Officer
eHMI	External Human-Machine Interface
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HAV	Highly Automated Vehicles
HRU	Human Road User
iHMI	Internal Human-Machine Interface
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
ODD	Operational Design Domain
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

Task 7.4 involves the overall management of Data, Ethics and Privacy, in which collected, processed or generated data will be described, as well as the methodologies and protocols that will be followed and whether data will be made public or not. The result of the task will be D7.2 Data Management Plan, submitted at M6 and updates to the deliverable in M12 and M18. The document defines how data used or produced within the project will be treated, archived, disseminated and maintained by project partners and how the data will be shared with the wider community.

1.2. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D7.4 is public and will therefore be made available on the website of the project, through an online tool and on the channels of the EC. This document is intended to be an internal guideline for the appropriate data management of the AWARE2ALL project.

2. Data summary

2.1. Purpose, relation to the objectives and utility

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards Highly Automated Vehicles (HAVs) deployment in traffic, by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and changes in the interaction of different road users caused by the emergence of HAV through the development of innovative technologies along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies. To this end, AWARE2ALL will develop inclusive and innovative safety (passive and active) and HMI (interior and exterior) systems that will consider the variety of population and will objectively demonstrate relevant improvements in mixed traffic safety.

In this sense, data gathering is closely related to all the objectives of the project:

- O1: Definition and prioritisation of relevant Use Cases to demonstrate and validate the project achievements, ensuring that most relevant safety critical situations related to future mixed traffic (external conditions) and occupant positions (internal conditions) are considered.
- O2: Develop one virtual prototype of passive safety (D1), based on a restraint system that extends the occupant protection range by addressing the variety of possible occupant postures and orientations. This prototype will take a large diversity of occupants into account, also considering additional information about body motion due to vehicle dynamics from pre-crash systems
- O3: Develop two active safety physical prototypes (D2, D3) to ensure that the vehicle is able to anticipate hazardous situations and act proactively. D2 will address Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB) and evasive manoeuvring for situations in which a driver is not available (e.g. shuttles). D3 will address transition of control strategies (handover/handback) for situations in which a driver is available (e.g. shared vehicle).
- O4: Development of a hybrid (virtual and physical) prototype (D3) of iHMI that will adapt, dynamically, the required bi-directional interaction with the driver/occupants, to either maintain certain situation awareness, or to nudge the occupants to the optimal state according to the evolving environment by proposing a new cognitive empathic augmented HMI. Methods, tools and mechanisms will be defined to determine the discrepancies between the measured or observed occupant states with respect to the determined optimal occupant state(s).
- O5: Current ODD definitions are only linked to the design parameters of sensors and functions and do not consider occupant state. AWARE2ALL propose the extension of the ODD definition by including occupant/driver state definition, e.g., even when a HAV is functioning well, if the system detects that the occupant(s) are not able to take over control when needed, it might decide to issue warnings or change vehicle behaviour (reduce speed, not perform any lane changes, ...).
- O6: Develop an eHMI physical prototype (D4) for effective communication and interaction with HRU. The system will include 2 modules: a perception system (to detect the type of user and the situation through image processing) and a communication system (additional components integrated with technologies using light and sounds to

adapt the message to the receiver and the situation). Focus will be the diversity of population (gender, age, digital ability, culture) and a framework for communication strategies will be developed.

- O7: Develop innovative testing methods and tools for performance assessment of AWARE2ALL safety and HMI solutions by using virtual and physical tools to validate the four demonstrators and showcase their impact in HAV safety for occupants and HRUs.

2.2. DMP online tool

The European Commission has long recognised that that research data is as important as any project publications or results. Furthermore, the value of data as a tangible resource fit for exploitation is continuously better recognised by the market, research communities, society and industry as a whole. This leads to a need for a structured approach to the use of research data within an applied research project that balances the need of all actors from a myriad of perspectives.

In addition to the obligation to publish in open access all scientific publications resulting from projects funded by Horizon Europe, projects must also aim to make available the research data needed to validate the results presented in these scientific publications, known as "underlying data". This must also be balanced with commercial concerns and, most importantly, with European and National Data Protection legislation.

In order to effectively integrate data into a project, create data within a project, and make available data external to a project, it is essential to consider how such data is managed at an early stage, and then continuously during its execution.

This DMP has been created by following the EC guidelines, including the use of the online tool recommended by them: Digital Curation Centre's DMP Online Tool.

When opening the DMP online tool a new plan can be created, and the EC can be chosen (among others) as the funding organisation. After choosing the funding organisation, DMPonline provides a set of questions to be answered that coincides with the questions proposed by the EC in the template provided in the guidelines, which help to ensure that there is no missing information.

There are three available DMPs to choose from, as recommended by the EC: the initial, to be submitted within the first 6 months of the project, which contains a brief set of questions; the detailed plan, to be updated at least in time with the periodic report; and the final one, to be updated in time for the final review. These last two plans contain a wider set of questions.

Template version 1, published on 16 May 2019

Initial DMP (6 sections, 9 questions)

Detailed DMP (9 sections, 31 questions)

Final review DMP (9 sections, 31 questions)

This tool also enables contributions from all partners, since they can be given access and all the consortium can see all the answers, which facilitates collaboration among partners.

3. Type of data

Throughout its lifetime, the AWARE2ALL project will generate and collect a variety of data, in different types and formats. The datasets to be collected or generated are relevant to the project system architecture. The following tables specify the data that the consortium expects to gather or generate, which have been divided into Demos and Generic data, to enable data tracking during the lifetime of the project. The tables below may be updated during the lifetime of the project, as the advancements of the workplan demand.

3.1. Data related to the Demos

Demo 1 – Passive Safety virtual prototype

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible (by the end of the project)
Model description	Description of simulation models, seating definitions and loading conditions	.json, .xml	Partially	Demo 1	Unknown	Yes
Animations, pictures	Structural integrity	.png, .jpg	No	Generated dataset	Unknown	Yes
Curve data	Acceleration outputs, intrusion values	.json, .csv	No	Generated dataset	Unknown	Yes
Model Output	Expected human injury values	.json	No	Generated dataset	Unknown	Yes

Vehicle crash performance data	Passive safety demo	Curve data, animations, pictures	No	Demo 1	Unknown	Yes, output for those related to and specified for the human injury values and structural assessment only. (input data used to create the numerical models and material descriptions, for example, cannot be shared)
Numerical Models	Virtual modelling and testing	CAD and/or CAE file (various formats)	Yes	THI, ESI, HUM, LS-Dyna	Unknown	No, for confidentiality reasons

Table 1 Demo 1 data

Demo 2 – Active safety

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Vehicle and sensor data	Active safety demo	Curve data, animations, pictures	No	Demo 2	Unknown	Yes
LiDAR pointclouds	Training DL algorithms for shuttle 3D detection from infrastructure	.pcd	No	Infrastructure LiDAR	Unknown	Yes

Videos	Occupant monitoring validation	.mp4	No	In cabin camera	Unknown	No, for confidentiality reasons
Videos	3D people detection from infrastructure	.mp4	No	Infrastructure camera	Unknown	No, for confidentiality reasons
Videos	3D people detection from shuttle	.mp4	No	Shuttle camera	Unknown	No, for confidentiality reasons

Table 2 Demo 2 data

Demo 3 – iHMI, OMS and Active Safety

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Videos	Training DL algorithms for driver monitoring systems	.mp4, .avi	Yes	Downloaded from dataset website	25TB of raw data	Yes
Radar reflection	Seat occupancy, respiration rate	Point-cloud, format not known at the moment	No	In cabin radar	Unknown	Yes
Reference kinematics	Reference kinematics	Joint angles, format not known at the moment	No	In cabin camera (AI pose estimation algorithm or motion capture)	Unknown	Yes
Reference respiration rate	Reference respiration rate	Timeseries, format not known at the moment	No	Human subject monitor	Unknown	Yes (anonymised)

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Participant subjective data	Research	Questionnaire. .csv, .mat, .docx,	No	WP2, WP3	Unknown	Yes, but only after a legal Data Sharing Agreement has been signed
Participant eye movement data	Research	.csv, .mat, .docx,	No	WP2, WP3	Unknown	
Participant driving behaviour data	Research	.csv, .mat, .docx,	No	WP2, WP3	Unknown	Yes, but only after a legal Data Sharing Agreement has been signed
Driving Performance parameters	Performance evaluation	.csv, .mat, pointclouds	No	Test sensors	Unknown	Yes
Driver Monitoring data	Driver behaviour assessment	.csv, .mat	No	Driver monitoring system	Unknown	No, for confidentiality reasons
Dataset of video streams	Training and validation of algorithm/model for DMS	.RGB/IR/RGB-IR and/or Pointcloud	No	Consortium partner	Unknown	No. Will be deleted the latest at the end of the project.
Videos	User tests analysis	.mp4	No	Demo 3	>400gb	No. Will be deleted the

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
						latest at the end of the project.
Participant Physiological data: Electroencephalogram (EEG) 5 channels	Input for the AI algorithm to estimate cognitive load	.xlsx with EEG values, timestamps (.csv)	No	Demo 3	Unknown	No, Will be deleted the latest at the end of the project.
Cognitive workload levels	Used to adapt the cockpit HMI in real time + user tests analysis	.xlsx (with binary values (0 or 1)), timestamps (.csv)	No	Demo 3	Unknown	Yes
Survey's responses with some personal data (age, driving experience, etc.)	Survey's responses with some personal data	.xlsx	No	Demo 3	Unknown	No. Will be deleted the latest at the end of the project.
Driving simulation data (including steering angle, speed, position in lane, pedals pressure, etc.)	User tests analysis	.xlsx	No	Demo 3	Unknown	Yes
GDPR file to anonymize data from participant gathered during the experiment	Anonymize experimental data	.xlsx	No	Demo 3	Unknown	No

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Participant personal data	Compare driving experience against other logged data. Make appointments for test sessions. To handle the financial compensation/travel reimbursement.	.xlsx, .docx	No	Demo 3	< 1MB	No. Will be deleted the latest at the end of the project.
Occupant Monitoring data	Training-, Test- and Validation dataset	.csv (tbc)	No	WP3, Demo 3	unknown	No, due to DP restrictions.

Table 3 Demo 3 data

Demo 4 – eHMI Physical Prototype

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
RGB Camera data	Training object detectors and human pose detectors for images	.png/.jpeg	Yes	Generated by Vicomtech, Mapillary, nuScenes	Unknown	Yes (anonymised)
User profiles	eHMI	.doc, .docx, .ppt, .pptx	Yes	User personas	20Mb	Yes
Recorded Video	Raw dataset to T&V our DL models (not for training)	.mp4	Yes	To be recorded in real environment	1GB	No, for confidentiality reasons

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Audio and vibration data for transducer calibration	eHMI audio warnings	.mp3, .WAV, waveforms, text files of audio and vibration data	No	Microphone measurements carried out by CEA	< 100 MB	Yes
Audio Outputs	eHMI audio messages	.mp3, .WAV,	No	Audio developed by Capgemini	< 100 MB	Yes
Consent forms for user tests	eHMI user tests	Electronic and/or paper	No	Consortium partner	10 MB	No, for confidentiality reasons
Photos and videos from user tests	eHMI	.png/.jpeg, .mp4	No	Consortium partner	20 MB	No, for confidentiality reasons
Warning signs to be used in lighting products	Determining the most accurate warning signs to be used in lighting products to ensure communication between the vehicle and other road users.	- .doc, .docx, .ppt, .pptx - .png/.jpeg, etc.), .DWG, .obj, .xls, .txt	Partially	Consortium partner, universal traffic warning signs and articles about warning signs.	Several hundred megabytes.	Yes

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Design of lighting products	To design lighting products in the most appropriate way	- CAD-Data of 3D parts(.stl, .step ...)(Mechanic, electrical, optic) - Measurement data in raw format (.csv, .xlsx) or report data format (.docx, .pdf) - Images and raw processed data (.png, .jpg)	Partially	Stop lamps taken from the relevant vehicle and used for benchmarking, and the previous work of the FEKA in this field.	Between 1 and 10 gigabytes.	Yes
Location of lighting products in the vehicle	Determining the position of the lighting lamps (especially the projection lamp) to be placed in the vehicle	.png,/.jpeg, CAD-Data of 3D parts (.stl, .step)	No	3D analysis.	Between 1 and 10 gigabytes.	Yes

Table 4 Demo 4 data

3.2. Generic data

Additionally, the AWARE2ALL consortium will also generate and collect data not directly related to the demonstrations.

Within the AWARE2ALL project, datasets will be subdivided as follows:

- Pilot-generated datasets that will be shared between the Consortium partners.
- Pilot-generated datasets that will be used for individual partner purposes (Private).

- Pilot-generated datasets that will be shared to the public (Open Data).
- Research findings and outcomes that will be publicly disseminated (Open Data).

The following table summarizes the data that the AWARE2ALL consortium expects to generate and collect:

Generic technical and non-technical data

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Synthetic data	Training vulnerable road users and increment the diversity of detectors	.png/.jpeg	No	Synthetic, generated by Vicomtech	Unkown	Yes
Reports	Definition, specification, Information, standardization, deliverables	Table/ Textfile (xlsx, docx, pdf, etc.)	No	Internal reports	< 500 KBs	Yes
Scientific papers	Dissemination	.pdf	Partially	Consortium	Unknown	Yes
User acceptance-Workshop	User Acceptance design	.docx	Yes	End users	Unknown	No, for confidentiality reasons
Consent forms for user tests	Human factor studies (T3.3), user tests (T5.2)	Electronic and/or paper	No	Consortium partner	1 GB	No, for confidentiality reasons
Subjective evaluation questionnaires	User acceptance evaluation	Electronic	No	External participants	Unknown	Yes, anonymized

Type of data	Purpose	Type and format	Re-used data	Origin	Expected size	Openly accessible
Demographic surveys	Sample characterization	Electronic	No	External participants	Unknown	Yes
Photos and Videos	Dissemination material for internal use, Social Media and press	.png/.jpeg, .ppt, .mp4, .docx	No	Data generated during meetings, Demos, Congressess, etc.	Unknown	Yes

Table 5 AWARE2ALL generic technical and non technical data

All these types of data in different formats and for different uses will be analysed by the partners case by case to study the potential conflicts related to commercialization/exploitation, legal or ethical uses.

However, and as a part of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) from the European Commission, apart from creating this DMP we will provide access to research data to the maximum extent. As described in the "*Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific publication and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*", Open access to research data refers to the right to access and reuse digital research data under the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement. The aim of AWARE2ALL is to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by the project, taking into account: the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and IPR, privacy concerns, security, and data management and preservation questions.

4. FAIR data

4.1. Making data Findable

Aside from justified exceptions, all the research data produced and/or used in the project will be discoverable with metadata (name, media presentation description, subtitles, tags, timeline content such as chat messages, multisensorial outputs), identifiable and locatable by means of standard identification mechanisms such as Digital Object Identifiers¹.

Search keywords will be provided to optimize possibilities for re-use and the following naming convention will be followed:

AWARE2ALL_[DATA-TYPE]_[DESCRIPTIVE-NAME]_[VERSION-NUMBER]

To facilitate finding but also handling research data produced by the AWARE2ALL project, clear version numbers and release notes (when applicable) will be provided.

To the maximum extent possible, metadata standards will be followed (e.g. SAE J3016 metadata standard for autonomous vehicles, or the MPEG-7 multimedia metadata standard). When needed, extensions to the existing standards will be used in the project and proposed as a contribution to the bodies responsible for maintaining those standards.

In a nutshell, in order to be able to retrieve and find data, the requirements have been listed below:

- (meta)data will be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- data will be described with rich metadata
- metadata will clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- (meta)data will be registered or indexed in a searchable resource

4.2. Making data openly Accessible

The aim of consortium is to make data generated by the project openly accessible to the fullest extent possible. However, the consortium will decide whether or not to make the data openly accessible when the data is generated. It will not be made open for reasons of confidentiality or commercial exploitation.

Data collected during validation and experimentation phases can be made accessible along with the produced software. In case of proprietary solutions, the code will reside in the company-specific repositories, while results from the experimentation can be made available and open. Openly accessible code will be deposited in repositories such as GitHub.

GDPR needs to be complied with so as to protect data and privacy, therefore, before making any content available, all data that fall into this category will be anonymised when possible.

The results of the research study are being made available to the public in an aggregated and anonymised form, and open access to research data will be granted. Moreover, open access to publications, 'gold' or 'green' open access are granted.

¹ <http://www.doi.org/>

Therefore, AWARE2ALL supports publications of scientific papers and generated datasets to open access journals and repositories as zenodo.org, arxiv.org and the European Open Science Cloud, which provide open access to scientific publications and the research outcomes following the FAIR guiding principles (making results Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). In order to fulfil with AWARE2ALL's commitment to Accessibility, a Zenodo community ([Zenodo AWARE2ALL Community](#)) was created, where public deliverables, scientific publications and public datasets are stored to support data reusability. All public resources are also available in the [project's own website](#). Some scientific papers will be posted on [ArXiv](#) due to copyright restrictions imposed by specific conference proceedings and journals.

4.3. Making data Interoperable

Data interoperability is achieved by means of the utilisation of international standards for data formatting (to provide harmonised structure), and via the definition or selection of vocabularies or ontologies (to provide semantics or meaning to data).

Regarding format, international standardisation bodies (e.g., SAE, ETSI, ISO, ASAM, etc.), are examined looking for published standards and recommendations that define data formats for the specific use cases. In case no standard is defined, or the field of application is too specific, data format shall be detailed and defined from project activities. Data files and payloads may in any case follow de-facto industry/academical formats (e.g., JSON and/or XML files for structured textual content, CSV text files for matrix data, H.264/5 or MPEG for video files, PCD for point clouds, etc.), to facilitate the utilisation of data with commonly used programming languages and tools.

Regarding semantics, in some cases, internationally acknowledged vocabularies or ontologies do not exist for a particular data type/use case. In these cases, if it is found unavoidable to use uncommon or to generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, the first approach will be to extend the existing ones (e.g., more generic vocabularies and ontologies from generic domains). If this option is not feasible, then mappings to more commonly used ontologies will be pursued. As of M18 of the project, this problem has not been encountered and therefore all public data is interoperable.

Whatever approach is followed, documentation shall be created which specifies the origin (external or project-specific) of the vocabularies and ontologies used to define the nomenclature required to provided meaning to data.

To be able to exchange data, the following requirements are met:

- (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

The data gathered will be analysed using open coding methodologies.

4.4. Making data Re-usable

For the data to be publicly available in Open Access platforms, the licences managed by such platforms (i.e., Common Creative 4.0 for Zenodo) has been adopted.

Figure 1 CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 licence term²

You are free to:

Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms.

Under the following terms:

- **Attribution** — You must give [appropriate credit](#), provide a link to the license, and [indicate if changes were made](#). You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
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In order to also facilitate the reutilisation of the produced data, its nature shall be documented (when data themselves are not self-explanatory) and provided along with the respected data, explaining its format, data model, used standards, method of extraction, means of manipulation, etc.

² <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>

5. Allocation of resources

All research data is collected by the data producers involved in the testing. AWARE2ALL partners take responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data.

VICOM leads the data management plan tasks and ensures project coordination in terms of the validation data collection, storage and handling. As coordinator of the process, VICOM also ensures that the data handled over the course of the project serve the project objectives by following up on the procedures to make data FAIR, secure and GDPR compliant.

With regards to Open Access to scientific publications, all AWARE2ALL partners that intend to publish scientific papers have budget allocated for conference and other dissemination costs (on top of travel and expenses). These budget allocations should allow covering (at least partially) of the costs of complying with the open data requirements of the project.

All the assets are safely stored in each partner's servers or in private servers secured by passwords. The data will be available for 5 years after the end of the project. Consent forms are kept in a safe place by the principal investigators and will be destroyed five years after the project has finished as long as it does not contradict internal rules of any of the consortium partners.

Each of the partners has appointed a data controller and processor when necessary, in compliance with the 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation.

Regarding the long-term preservation of data, partners have allocated resources related to the purchase of the needed storage.

On the other hand, data gathered by trials will be stored on hard drives and box files if it is not digital; and therefore, costs of preservation will be minimal.

6. Data protection and ethical aspects

6.1. Compliance with GDPR

The approach proposed to handle the GDPR in AWARE2ALL project consists of identifying all the concerned parties and the actions they need to take in order to comply with the regulation. This approach will enforce that personal data collected in AWARE2ALL shall be (Article 5 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation):

- Processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to individuals.
- Collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and further processed for scientific purposes.
- Adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the purposes for which they are processed.
- Kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed.
- Processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage. Further refinement of the above-mentioned approach will be provided in next versions of this deliverable.

In general, each partner (data generator and processor) will be responsible for complying with the relevant rules. However, central (project-level) monitoring of such compliance will be ensured as well.

6.2. Data protection

VICOM also acts as Data Protection Officer for the AWARE2ALL project: Dorleta García has been appointed as Data Management and Protection Officer (DMPO). This Manager/Officer raises potential issues and proposes solutions for dealing adequately with data privacy and data protection regulations and will also liaise with the partners who will perform the demonstrations and the testbed members to ensure proper application of the Data Protection policies at the national level.

The responsibilities of the DPO will be in line with Article 39 of the GDPR and will include, at a minimum, the following:

- Advise data controllers and processors within the 5GMETA project on the processing of personal data, training of researchers and assignment of responsibilities.
- Provide support on the performance and tracking of Impact Assessments.
- Assist in risk assessment of personal data processing.
- Cooperate with any national or European supervisory authority and act as contact point for the project with such authorities.

6.3. Ethical aspects

The acquisition and processing of data in AWARE2ALL follows these general principles that apply to all kinds of data usage:

- **Participation:** All activities shall be conducted with fully rational adults on a strictly voluntary basis. They must be in a position to understand their role in the project and be able to give consent. At no point will AWARE2ALL engage in research concerning vulnerable persons. Participation in the field trials of AWARE2ALL will be open to any age, disability and gender, give that they are main target users for the project.
- **Withdrawal:** AWARE2ALL is aware that some individuals may find engagement with new forms of developed technology stressful or unpleasant. Any participant will be able to withdraw from the use cases at any time without suffering any detrimental effect.
- **Data minimization:** The collection and the processing activities on the personal data of research participants will be performed in accordance with the principles of data protection, notably the principle of data minimisation, which aims to limit the interference with the person's personal information, while ensuring data quality and confidentiality.
- **Informed Consent:** Personal data will be processed in the AWARE2ALL project on the basis of informed consent
- **Anonymization:** After acquisition all data will be anonymized before any further processing. The anonymization will be conducted by the respective partner who obtains the data from the research participants.
- **Data transfer:** The data will be transferred only within the project consortium and only for specific research purposes (principle of purpose specification).
- **Data storage:** Precautionary actions are taken to ensure that personal data are stored securely.
- **Storage time:** Personal data will be anonymized right after it is gathered and combined with other data of the respective research participants. All data will be kept and processed only for the duration of the project. Thereafter all data will be erased. There will be no non-disclosure limitation formalised in the grant agreement. Storage time may vary according to the internal rules of each organisation. For example, TNO has a different policy in this respect: as long as the data is anonymised, they obtain the participant's consent to reuse it without time limit.
- **Research transparency:** Prior to any involvement in the validation of AWARE2ALL platform, the voluntary participants will be handed over a project information sheet

Activities performed in AWARE2ALL will not represent any harm of any type.

The consortium is fully aware of the ethical implications of the proposed research and respects the ethical rules and standards of Horizon Europe, and those reflected in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. Generally speaking, ethical, social and data protection considerations are crucial to this project and will be given all due attention. The consortium is aware that a number of ethical, privacy and data protection issues may be raised by the activities to be performed in the scope of the project and includes the necessary precautions and actions to guard against misuse. For this reason, since human participants are

involved in certain aspects of the project and data is collected, this will be done in full compliance of the main legislation and directives and more specifically:

- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data.
- The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms.
- Directive 95/46/EC & Directive 2002/58/EC of the European parliament regarding issues with privacy and protection of personal data and the free movement of such data.
- Directive 2001/20/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use.
- Council Directive 83/570/EEC of 26 October 1983 amending Directives 65/65/EEC, 75/318/EEC and 75/319/EEC on the approximation laid down by law, regulation or administrative action relating to proprietary medicinal products.
- Directive 98/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 1998 on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions.
- Directive on Privacy and Electronic Communications (2002/58/EC)
- Directive on Protection of Privacy in the Telecommunication Sector (97/66/EC)

Since the AWARE2ALL research activities involve human participants in the research and evaluation processes, the required process is to obtain informed consent. In order to do so, both the Information Sheets and the Informed Consent Forms has been designed, provided and kept on file during and after the project.

Information sheets and informed consents will be generally provided in writing. However, if consent cannot be given in writing, non-written consent will be formally documented. Appropriate efforts will be made to ensure fully informed understanding of the implications of participations, providing alternative communication means if necessary. Information sheets and consent forms are written in a way that participants can fully understand. However, specific adaptations may need to be made to adapt to the specific user needs. More specifically:

- An oral information sheet and consent form can be administered orally if this is better suited for end users' needs.
- Sign Language versions can be provided if needed.

This means that information sheets and informed consents will be generally provided in writing.

Below can be found both the information sheet and the consent form that will be used with the participants. These forms can be translated into the language desired by each partner.

6.3.1. AWARE2ALL Information Sheet

AWARE2ALL – Safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to diverse population towards future scenarios with increasing share of highly automated vehicles	AWARE2ALL
HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-01-02	
INFORMATION SHEET	

INFORMATION

Project: AWARE2ALL

Main researcher: Oihana Otaegui

Ethical adviser: Monica Diaz de Medivil

AWARE2ALL aims to pave the way towards the deployment in traffic of highly automated vehicles (HAV) – Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) presenting SAE-L4 features – by effectively addressing the changes in road safety and in the interaction of different human road users (HRUs) caused by the emergence of HAV. The project will develop safety systems adapted to these new scenarios in mixed traffic along with the corresponding assessment tools and methodologies. This idea is new and experimental, so we need to understand what works – and what could be better. For that reason, we will gather information about:

- What happens in the project
- *Other aspects to be defined during the project*

This information will help us improve future work and prepare tools and guidance for others who want to work like this in future. It will also allow us to report on what has been done to the EU which has financed the project and to the people who take part.

You will be asked for some details about yourself. Then, you will be asked to give your opinion on various aspects of your experience in the project. We hope that this explanation is clear, but if you want to know more, please just ask us.

If you encounter any type of discomfort you can stop at any time without prior justification.

Now please read the consent form.

AWARE2ALL – Safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to diverse population towards future scenarios with increasing share of highly automated vehicles

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 861570 (Research and Innovation Action)

6.3.2. AWARE2ALL Informed Consent Form

<p>AWARE2ALL – Safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to diverse population towards future scenarios with increasing share of highly automated vehicles</p> <p>HORIZON-CL5-2022-D6-01-02</p>	<p>AWARE2ALL</p>
<p>CONSENT FORM</p>	

In this [focus group/questionnaire/interview/driving simulator experiment], we want to evaluate the impact of access to car data coming from relevant geographical regions in the generation of new opportunities and business models for different actors. This will allow us to identify the needs of diverse stakeholders and research how the quality of experience and the quality of the service can be improved.

The information you provide will be used in the project, but it will remain anonymous. All information that you give will be treated in the strictest confidence and it will only be used for the purposes of this study. No personal data will be collected that permits your identification. This consent will be kept in a safe place by the principal investigators and will be destroyed five years after the investigation has finished. Once the study has been completed and the data analysed, the entire database will be available to other interested researchers after five years after the project has been completed.

Your participation in this study is absolutely voluntary, and there is not economic compensation. There is no penalty for not participating and there are no risks of any kind in your participation. You can discontinue your involvement in the study at any time without prior justification. This shall have no repercussions or negative consequences of any sort.

AWARE2ALL is a European project led by VICOMTECH (Spain). The ethical adviser responsible of ethical procedures is Monica Diaz de Mendivil. You can contact Monica Diaz de Mendivil at mdiazdemendivil@vicomtech.org and ask for more information about the project and the project results. The researcher administering the test is (NAME and SURNAME).

If you are willing to participate, please confirm the following statements by signing at the end of this document

- I have read and understood the information given for this research or have had the information read to me,
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the research.
- I consent to take part in the research sessions.

Name of the participant Date Signature

Name of the researcher Date Signature

AWARE2ALL – Safety systems and human-machine interfaces oriented to diverse population towards future scenarios with increasing share of highly automated vehicles

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 861570 (Research and Innovation Action)

7. Data security

The data produced during AWARE2ALL is stored per trial site in local servers and in central servers for the whole project. Those data shall be processed in compliance with the GDPR. This chapter describes some security principles to be implemented in order to protect against any type of modification. These security principles are listed below:

- Authentication: users requiring access to AWARE2ALL data servers should be authenticated; also, proper means are used to authenticate the servers.
- Authorization: access to AWARE2ALL data servers is only available to the authenticated and authorized users. These categories and the rights of those users are defined and enforced. The appropriate access control policies and mechanisms (including physical access control) shall be identified for each trial site and project wide to provide the authorization.
- Accounting: any access and modification to a resource by any user is securely logged in order to prevent users from denying that data files were accessed, altered or deleted. Other accounting mechanisms shall be implemented.
- Confidentiality: data stored in AWARE2ALL servers shall be encrypted during transmission and storage.
- Communication Security: access to AWARE2ALL servers shall be done through encrypted communication channels such as HTTPS.
- Availability: this security principle assures that AWARE2ALL servers shall be available for AWARE2ALL users during the defined interval of service. Also, regular backups of the data shall be made.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable D7.4 Data Management Plan represents the first update of AWARE2ALL Data Management Plan. Throughout this document we have identified the data that is being generated by the project, how to make it Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable, the allocation of resources needed to maintain the data FAIR, and the ethical and security aspects of data collection that are anticipated at this point of the project.

This first update of the Data Management Plan summarises the intention of the project in relation to the data to be openly accessible, described in Section 3. The datasets to be collected or generated throughout the lifetime of the project are related to the four Demonstrators of the project, namely, Passive Safety virtual prototype, Active safety, iHMI, OMS and Active Safety and eHMI Physical Prototype. Additionally, the project will generate generic datasets like deliverables, scientific papers and presentations.

This Plan will be further updated at the end of the project, providing the final version of the datasets, as well as the links where they will be published following the FAIR principles.

9. References

- Digital Curation Centre's DMP Online Tool. Accesible at: <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/plans>
- European Commission, 2017: Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, version 3.2.
- European Commission, 2016: H2020 Programme – Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, version 3.0 (https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf)
- European Commission 2015: Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020, version 2.0.
- European Commission, 2016: Guidelines to FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020, version 3.0.

